

Semiconductor Substrates in Phased Arrays - Integration Issues, Challenges and Laboratory Results¹²

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Abstract—This paper will discuss the ongoing research being conducted in the RF Technology Division of the Applied Sensors, Guidance, and Electronics Directorate, US Army Aviation and Missile Research, Development, and Engineering Center (AMRDEC) on the Redstone Arsenal in Huntsville, Alabama. The overall purpose of the research is to determine and overcome the technological barriers impinging upon enhancements to current phased array technology which is expected to include MEMS in addition to chip-level integration of multiple phased array components. An overview of phased array systems and components will be presented along with applications and insertion into potential military systems and the benefits thereof. The paper will discuss the current research effort and future research areas for this project and its benefits in creating an air defense system to support the Future Combat System (FCS) of the US Army.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

This paper is an exploration of the current efforts being conducted at the US Army Aviation and Missile Research, Development and Engineering Center. The initial work for this research was presented in Technical Report AMR-SG-04-13 titled “Low-Cost, Low-Loss Phased Arrays Using

Highest Level of Component Integration” and Technical Report AMR-SG-05-14 titled “Design and Simulation of Patch Antenna Elements onto Semiconductor Substrates for use in Phased Arrays. Early surveys of industry and academia to determine the state-of-the-art in phased array systems showed that the major barriers impinging upon continued wafer-level component integration (along with the radiating elements associated with the array) included heat dissipation and thermal management, packaging, shielding of radiation from micro- or nano-electronic circuitry, and quantification of any electromagnetic interactions between radiating elements and the semiconductor substrate. In addition, the possible benefits of RF MEMS, when used to create phasing networks, are an exciting area of research which is constantly being monitored throughout this effort. The main purpose of the current analysis is to quantify electromagnetic interactions through a study of the propagation characteristics of plane waves in semiconductor materials. Through this study, I hope to determine the degree to which a semiconductor acts as a good dielectric substrate for an antenna and also the degree to which an electromagnetic wave will propagate through the substrate, possibly causing interference to nearby devices.

A complete system-level integration of an entire millimeter-wave active array using semiconductor substrates will result in higher overall performance with lower losses. The high-integration, single packaging of Phased Array Modules (PAMs) will result in an overall effective gain due to the reduction of loss experienced due to multiple packaging of individual components or subcomponents. Mono-package fabrication greatly reduces the losses experienced by single component packaging. For example, a single MEMS switch, at die level, typically exhibits a 0.2 dB loss. Once packaged, the switch exhibits an approximate loss of 2 to 2.5 dB.

But why semiconductor substrates? Semiconductor

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substrate-based radiating elements present an opportunity for “one-stop” fabrication. In other words, the radiating element associated with a particular phase shifter could be fabricated on the same substrate at the same time as the phase shifter of that element. In addition – it leads to the possibility of a full array fabrication on a single wafer as yield values increase. By changing the doping patterns of the substrate, the use of semiconductor materials present some interesting design opportunities for windowing, or weighting of elements based on the resistivity of the material.

2.0 PHASED ARRAY SYSTEMS

For completion, the following background on phased array systems, their benefits and components has been included in this paper. This information, with some minor changes, was taken from the 2004 IEEE Aerospace Conference paper given on this research subject [1].

A phased array antenna system is a compilation of several radiating elements set at a specific distance from each other to enhance the final radiation beam formation. By changing the phase of each of the radiating elements, it is possible to steer the beam to a desired position very quickly and without the need for mechanical positioning. A more complete introduction to phased array systems can be found in [1] and in many other classic texts.

There are many benefits of Electronically steerable, phased arrays (ESA) in the defense industry – particularly when used in missile seeker systems. In such a small confined space, it is immediately evident that larger, gimbaled seeker systems require a great deal more area than an electronically steerable array. In addition, power requirements and heat management requirements must be addressed. Active array prime power requirements are significantly less than conventional phased array requirements and are expected to continue to improve as the power added efficiency of power ICs increases [2].

Other benefits include the ability to offer rapid beam steering, element weighting and multiple beam generation. Rapid beam steering can be utilized to switch between multiple incoming targets or multiple beam generation can be used to track multiple targets at the same time. Monopulse tracking is easily obtained through multiple beam generation by segmentation of the beam into four quadrants to track incoming targets via delta azimuth and delta elevation signals. Electronically steerable, phased arrays can be used in Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems to image a scene which can then be matched to information provided from an external sensor to identify the most desirable target [3]. More of the advantages of the ESA can be found in [4].

Historically, electronically steerable phased arrays are

designed in two ways, the passive ESA which utilizes a single transmitter and receiver and the active ESA that utilizes multiple Transmit/Receive (T/R) modules, typically one per radiating element. Of particular interest here is the location of the Low Noise Amplifier (LNA) in relation to the radiating elements. To achieve the best performance from the array, the LNA needs to be located as close as possible to the radiating elements so that very little signal loss occurs before the first amplification on receive. In the passive ESA design, the phasing network is placed between the LNA and the radiating elements. This layout increases the noise level in the system as the signal experiences loss traveling through the phasing network. The passive array utilizes only one, high power transmitter.

In the active ESA design, each radiating element is fed by an individual T/R module each with low peak power compared to the single transmitter in the passive array design. In this case, the LNA can be positioned immediately after the radiating element and the location of the phasing network is not of major concern. Figure 1 gives a comparison of the passive and active array designs [5].

To create circuits with such high levels of integration on a single substrate requires an exceptional level of reliability from each of the individual components used in the final system. Fortunately, phased arrays are considered to have graceful degradation in that a few components can fail and the entire system still performs with modest reliability. Regardless, in a military environment and especially in a missile seeker, the reliability of the components is a key performance parameter of the overall system. Some of the components of the phased array will be discussed below along with their functions and possible problems associated with the integration of these components.

A simple layout of a radiating element and its associated T/R module, including phasing network, is shown in Figure 2 [6]. This combination of the standard T/R module and a radiating element associated with the T/R module is known as a Phased Array Module (PAM). This design utilizes only one phase shifter for both the transmit and receive chains. In many cases, the phase shift operation is performed at RF, not always IF as the figure shows.

Figure 1. Comparison of Passive and Active Array Designs

Figure 2. Simple Schematic of a Phased Array Module

A key component of the receiving side of a T/R module is the Low Noise Amplifier (LNA). The function of the LNA is to amplify the signal, doing so with the addition of very little new noise. This component should be located as close as possible to the radiating element so that it captures the incoming signal and amplifies it before any additional losses or noise are experienced due to other components. The goal is that the gain of the LNA should be large enough so that it overcomes the addition of noise that will be contributed by the rest of the system. Because of these characteristics, the LNA gain and noise figure determine the noise characteristics of the receiver. Following the LNA, the signal passes through a narrow-band filter and into the mixer where it is down-converted to an Intermediate Frequency (IF). This down-conversion is accomplished by mixing the RF signal with a signal generated in the Local Oscillator (LO). The results of this mixing generates not only the IF ($f_{RF} - f_{LO}$ or $f_{LO} - f_{RF}$), but also harmonics of the IF, LO, and RF frequencies which must be filtered out. From here, the signal passes through the phase shifter and eventually on to the signal processor [6].

The transmit side of the module uses many of the same components as the receiver. Like the receiving side of the module, the signal is upconverted to RF and then passes through a phasing network. The key component of the transmit side is the Power Amplifier (PA). Because solid state amplifiers are low power, several devices (transistors) are required to generate the power needed for most phased array applications. The large numbers of transistors in combination create an immediate need for heat dissipation. This can be accomplished by fabricating the devices on a thin wafer which reduces the transmission path from the heat source to a heat spreading material such as Silicon Carbide (SiC) or diamond, or by creating a thermal management within the layers of the substrate itself [6].

3.0 RESEARCH AREAS FOR PHASED ARRAY ENHANCEMENTS

One area of research for phased array enhancements involves the use of RF MEMS (Microelectromechanical Systems) switches in phasing networks. To support this research, the RDEC is exploring piezoelectrically actuated structures for RF MEMS switches that offer relatively large actuation forces compared to the alternatives, thus offering the promise of reducing stiction efforts and thereby increasing reliability [7, 8, 9]. In addition, we are constantly monitoring the progress of commercially available switches for possible use in phasing networks.

MEMS switches present an opportunity for greater cost savings by reducing the number of Transmit/Receive (T/R) modules needed in an active array system. In current active array designs, the Low Noise Amplifier (LNA) is located immediately adjacent to the radiating element, hereby

amplifying the received signal at the earliest point while adding very little noise as shown in some of the current design configurations in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 3. A single T/R Module per radiating element, single phasing network located away from the radiating element.

Because MEMS switches are low-loss devices, it is believed that MEMS switches will create an opportunity to locate a phasing network between the radiating element and the LNA. This will increase the potential cost savings of MEMS by allowing designs in which one T/R module feeds several radiating elements. Current T/R modules, particularly PHEMT designs, are capable of operation at voltages exceeding 10 Volts thereby allowing the component to produce the necessary power to drive multiple radiating elements as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Possible design with low-loss phasing network in which one T/R module feeds several radiating elements.

In an expendable device such as a missile seeker system it is increasingly necessary to reduce cost while maintaining overall high performance levels. T/R modules are a large part of the overall cost in a phased array system, due to their highly fabrication intensive substrates. A reduction in the number of necessary T/R modules will greatly impact the overall cost of the system and the small loss associated with the location of the phasing network can be overcome through engineering trades in performance enhancements.

Current unpackaged MEMS switches exhibit losses of approximately 0.2 to 0.5 dB at Ku- to Ka-band frequencies. Packaging of the switches greatly enhances this loss, often increasing to 2.5 dB per switch. This leads to another phased array enhancement possibility – not only in the area of MEMS phasing networks, but for the overall system – higher levels of component integration onto a single substrate with minimal packaging of entire subsystems.

The main purpose of the research effort is to explore the highest possible integration upon a single chip, or wafer, for use in phased arrays including the inclusion of the radiating element and the necessary feed networks to connect each radiating element to its associated T/R Module. To begin with, consider a single radiating element fabricated on a silicon, GaAs, or InP chip. With the large amount of space between the elements of a phased array utilizing $\lambda/2$ spacing (or near equivalent), it makes sense to include T/R Modules, phasing networks and the logic control needed to drive the system on the same chip. In addition, the back side of the chip can be utilized if necessary and fed with vias.

Current technology trends in the field of T/R Modules for phased arrays are centered on the use of the High-Electron-Mobility Transistor (HEMT). The choice for high frequencies where low noise figures are required (such as in missile seeker applications utilizing T/R modules) are the GaAs and InP substrate based HEMT devices [10]. These substrates are highly fabrication intensive and therefore expensive. It does not make sense to move additional devices onto these costly substrates. Instead, this research is centered on moving the HEMT substrate T/R Module onto a much cheaper semiconductor substrate. The T/R Module can be flip-chipped (preferred) or ribbon bonded to the cheaper semiconductor substrate. Additional information on current technology trends in T/R Modules can be found in [1].

4.0 ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVE PROPAGATION

To determine the feasibility of semiconductor substrates for use as a dielectric in antenna designs let us consider a plane wave analysis using semiconductor materials as the dielectric substrates. To begin with, we will consider the most basic and well-known semiconductors. We will begin by looking at intrinsic semiconductors and we will take the relative permeability (μ_r) of all semiconductors to be 1. The conductivity values of these materials are approximate. Conductivity in semiconductors increases with temperature and is often noted as thermal conductivity. The values stated in this paper deal with electrical conductivity, assumed to be at room temperature.

Table 1 contains values for some common intrinsic semiconductor substrates. The first analysis will consider an Electromagnetic (EM) plane wave present in a bulk semiconductor medium. This case represents the creation of an Electric field within the semiconductor itself and studies the attenuation as it propagates through the material. The purpose of this analysis is to determine the attenuation of the power of the EM wave as it propagates through the material and provide data that would support the location of other devices on the same substrate that might be affected by the location of EM energy on the same substrate.

Table 1. Properties of Some Common Intrinsic Semiconductors

	Silicon (Si)	Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)	Germanium (Ge)
Relative Permittivity (ϵ_r)	11.9	13.1	16.0
Relative Permeability (μ_r)*	1	1	1
Conductivity (σ)	4.39×10^{-4}	8×10^{-3}	2.227

Figure 5 is a visual representation of the first analysis to be performed:

Figure 5. Visual Representation of the First Analysis

For this analysis, let us begin with Maxwell's Equations and derive the wave equation:

$$\nabla_x \bar{E} = -j\omega\mu\bar{H} \text{ and } \nabla_x \bar{H} = j\omega\epsilon\bar{E} \quad (1)$$

Using the first equation, take the curl of both sides to get:

$$\nabla_x \nabla_x \bar{E} = -j\omega\mu(\nabla_x \bar{H}) \quad (2)$$

Note that $\nabla_x \nabla_x \bar{E} = \nabla \nabla \cdot \bar{E} - \nabla^2 \bar{E}$. If there are no sources present, $\nabla \cdot \bar{D} = 0$, and $\nabla_x \nabla_x \bar{E} = -\nabla^2 \bar{E}$. Thus, the wave equation becomes

$$\nabla^2 \bar{E} + \omega^2 \mu\epsilon \bar{E} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Taking \bar{E} to be polarized in only the x-direction, and having an amplitude of E_o , a possible solution of the wave equation is

$$E_x(z) = E_o e^{-\gamma z} \quad (4)$$

Where γ is a complex propagation constant (in radians per meter), or $\gamma = \alpha + j\beta$ and $\gamma^2 = j\omega\mu(\sigma + j\omega\epsilon)$ where α describes the attenuation, or power loss, that the EM wave experiences as it propagates due to the lossy dielectric. The values of α and β can be obtained by solving for the real (α) and imaginary (β) parts of γ using the wave equation,

$$\alpha = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu\epsilon}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left[\frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon} \right]^2} - 1 \right]} \quad (5)$$

$$\beta = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu\epsilon}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left[\frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon} \right]^2} + 1 \right]} \quad (6)$$

The following table gives the values obtained for α and β for several intrinsic semiconductor substrates.

Table 2. Propagation Constants

	Silicon (Si)	Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)	Germanium (Ge)
α	0.0235	0.4163	104.8055
β	2530.5	2655.0	2936.1

The addition of Germanium with its large attenuation value makes a direct comparison of all three materials difficult.

Figure 6 shows the comparison of Si and GaAs normalized attenuation as a function of distance, z and Figure 7 shows the normalized attenuation of Germanium as a function of distance, z .

Figure 6. Normalized Attenuation as a Function of Distance

Figure 7. Normalized Attenuation as a Function of Distance

Notice that due to its much higher conductivity value, electromagnetic waves traveling in Germanium experience a greater attenuation than those in Silicon or GaAs.

Next, let's consider impure, or doped, semiconductor values. Figure 8 below, taken from [11] shows resistivity values for silicon for both n-type and p-type dopant at 300K (room temperature) and figure 9 shows the values for germanium and gallium arsenide.

Figure 8. Resistivity Values for Silicon at Room Temperature

Figure 9. Resistivity Values for GaAs and Ge at Room Temperature

different material's attenuation values is included. This shows the major difference attributed to the much larger dielectric constant of germanium as compared to that of silicon and gallium arsenide. From the plots below it is easy to see that the effects of doping greatly negate the contribution of the dielectric constant of the material.

To study the effects of doping on electromagnetic wave propagation, we will choose a few values of conductivity and plot the attenuation as a function of distance, z , as we did for the pure case. Looking at conductivity values of 250, 500, 750 and 1000 (larger doping quickly increases these values, up to 10^6 and beyond, but at this point and silicon gives the results of Figure 11.

To best study the effects of doping on electromagnetic wave propagation, we will look at the range of resistivity values – from 10^{-4} to 10^3 ohm-cm (or 10^{-6} to 10^1 ohm-m) and compute the conductivity (at room temperature) for each value from

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho}, \quad (\text{S/m}) \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the resistivity values, ranging from 10^{-4} to 10^3 ohm-cm, and σ is the conductivity which ranges from 10^{-3} to 10^4 . Figure 10 shows the attenuation value, α , for each of the three semiconductors of interest as a function of the conductivity value.

Notice that the three semiconductor attenuation values are very similar and may, at first, appear to be identical so an exploded view showing the differences between the three

Figure 10. Attenuation Value of EM Wave in Doped Semiconductor

Figure 11. Attenuation of EM Wave in Doped Semiconductor

Here again, the plots line up for each value. An exploded view is shown in the inset which also identifies which grouping corresponds to each conductivity value.

From this plot, it is easy to see that the electromagnetic wave attenuates quickly for larger values of conductivity (as expected) and for even smaller values. For another device located in the vicinity of the included radiating element, the strength of the electromagnetic wave is decreased to less than $1/10^{\text{th}}$ of its original value at a distance of 1mm from the object for values of conductivities listed above. Thus, we can conclude that other semiconductor devices, such as p-n junction devices, would experience little effect from the electromagnetic wave propagation if the area between the device and the radiation source contained impurities leading to conductivities such as those in the plot above. The proximity of other devices to the radiation source should be determined by possible interactions between the wave strength at that location and known threshold voltages of the devices.

Assuming y-independence, the following is a visual representation of the second analysis to be performed, where the Electromagnetic (EM) Wave is incident upon a slab of silicon denoted by $\mu_1 \epsilon_1$ from freespace. This would most represent a case where a radiating element such as a patch antenna is fabricated on the surface of the substrate and electromagnetic energy enters the substrate from back or side lobes of the radiation pattern. Thus, some of the traveling energy is reflected and only a portion of the energy actually enters the semiconductor.

Let the Electric Field be polarized in the y direction, or perpendicular to the plane of wave propagation (perpendicular polarization).

Figure 12. Second Analysis Visualization

Note that the EM wave is denoted by the vector \mathbf{k} , incident

upon the silicon slab at an angle θ_i , and traveling through the silicon at an angle θ_t .

$$\mathbf{k}_i = \beta_i \hat{x} + q_i \hat{z} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\mathbf{k}_r = \beta_r \hat{x} - q_r \hat{z} \quad (9)$$

or

$$\mathbf{k}_i = \omega \sqrt{\mu_1 \epsilon_1} (\sin \theta_i \hat{x} + \cos \theta_i \hat{z}) \quad (10)$$

and

$$\mathbf{k}_r = \omega \sqrt{\mu_1 \epsilon_1} (\sin \theta_i \hat{x} - \cos \theta_i \hat{z}) \quad (11)$$

From Maxwell's Equations:

$$\nabla_x \bar{E} = -j\omega \mu \bar{H} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\nabla_x \bar{H} = j\omega \epsilon \bar{E}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} are the electric and magnetic field vectors.

Assuming soft, or perpendicular polarization and an incident Electric field

$$E_{yi} = E_o e^{-jq_i z - j\beta_i x} = E_o e^{-j\vec{k}_i \cdot \vec{r}}, \quad (14)$$

where k_i and r are vectors.

Thus, in Region 1, the incident region, the total fields present are:

$$E_{yi} = E_o e^{-jq_i z - j\beta_i x} = E_o e^{-j\vec{k}_i \cdot \vec{r}} \quad (15)$$

and

$$E_{yr} = E_r e^{jq_r z - j\beta_r x} = E_r e^{-j\vec{k}_r \cdot \vec{r}} \quad (16)$$

In Region 2, the total fields present are the transmitted fields:

$$E_{yt} = E_t e^{-jq_t z - j\beta_t x} = E_t e^{-j\vec{k}_t \cdot \vec{r}} \quad (17)$$

Using Maxwell's Equations, (any region):

$$\bar{H} = \frac{-1}{j\omega\mu} \nabla_x \bar{E} \quad (18)$$

Looking at the tangential component which is the \hat{x} component,

$$H_x = \frac{1}{j\omega\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} E_y \quad (19)$$

$$\text{So, } H_{xi} = -\frac{E_{yi}}{Z_1}, \quad Z_1 = \frac{\omega\mu_1}{q_1} \quad (20, 21)$$

$$\text{and } H_{xr} = \frac{E_{yr}}{Z_r}, \quad Z_r = \frac{\omega\mu_1}{q_1} \quad (22, 23)$$

and
$$H_{xt} = -\frac{E_{yt}}{Z_t}, \quad Z_t = \frac{\omega\mu_t}{q_t} \quad (24, 25)$$

Note that $(q_{i,r})^2 + (\beta_{i,r})^2 = \omega^2\mu_i\epsilon_i$ and $q_i^2 + \beta_i^2 = \omega^2\mu_2\epsilon_2$.

Matching boundary conditions at the boundary between Region 1 and Region 2 yields the following two equations:

$$1) (E_{yi} + E_{yr})|_{z=0^-} = E_{yt}|_{z=0^+} \quad (26)$$

$$2) (H_{xi} + H_{xr})|_{z=0^-} = H_{xt}|_{z=0^+} \quad (27)$$

Because of phase matching constraints $\beta_i = \beta_r = \beta_t = \beta$ and $q_i = q_r = q_t = q$.

Thus, these two boundary matching equations yield the following 2 equations, and 2 unknowns:

$$1) E_o e^{-j\beta x} + E_r e^{-j\beta x} = E_t e^{-j\beta x} \quad (28)$$

$$2) \frac{-E_o}{Z_1} e^{-j\beta x} + \frac{E_r}{Z_r} e^{-j\beta x} = \frac{-E_t}{Z_t} e^{-j\beta x} \quad (29)$$

From these two equations E_r and E_t can be found. The transmit angle, θ_t , can be found using Snell's Law: $n_1 \sin\theta_i = n_2 \sin\theta_t$ where $n_1 = \sqrt{\mu_{r1}\epsilon_{r1}}$ and $n_2 = \sqrt{\mu_{r2}\epsilon_{r2}}$ with μ_r, ϵ_r being relative permeability and relative permittivity.

Taking E_o to be 1 (normalized), we can use the values of $Z_1, Z_r,$ and Z_t to find E_r and E_t :

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_o + E_r \\ \frac{E_o - E_r}{Z_1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_t \\ \frac{E_t}{Z_t} \end{bmatrix}$$

Choosing an incident angle of 30° , the following parameters were obtained:

Table 3. Parameter Values for an Incident Angle of 30°

	Silicon (Si)	Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)	Germanium (Ge)
Relative Permittivity (ϵ_r)	11.9	13.1	16.0
Relative Permeability (μ_r)*	1	1	1
Conductivity (σ)	4.39×10^{-4}	8×10^{-3}	2.227
$\epsilon_{complex}$	1.0536e-10 -1.9553e-15i	1.1599e-1 -3.6378e-14i	1.4167e-1 -1.0127e-11i
q_i	2.1914e+3 -2.0334e-2i	2.2993e+3 -3.6057e-1i	2.5427e+3 -9.0764e+1i
β_i	1.2652e+3 -1.1740e-2i	1.3275e+3 -2.0817e-1i	1.4680e+3 -5.2403e+1i
n_1	1	1	1
n_2	3.4496	3.6194	4
Z_1	435.0107	435.0107	435.0107
Z_t	1.2610e+2 +1.1701e-3i	1.2019e+2 +1.8848e-2i	1.0855e+2 +3.8746i
Z_r	435.0107	435.0107	435.0107
E_o	1	1	1
E_t	0.4495	0.4330	0.3995
E_r	-0.5505	-0.5670	-0.6005

Since we have taken E_o to be one (normalized), the values of the transmission coefficient, $\tau = E_t / E_o$ and the reflection coefficient, $\Gamma = E_r / E_o$ become $\tau = E_t$ and $\Gamma = E_r$. Thus the transmitted portion of the electromagnetic energy is reduced to less than half the original values for all three materials under study. Also, notice that the values of E_r are negative; this is due to the change of direction of the wave vector in the z direction as expected.

The plots of transmitted wave amplitude are shown in Figure 13.

Thus, it is easy to see that the worst case scenario would be for an electromagnetic wave that is generated within the semiconductor substrate and that for radiation generated outside the substrate, only a portion of the energy is actually transmitted into the substrate.

Figure 13. Attenuation of EM Wave in Doped Material, Transmitted Wave

5.0 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The resulting plots show that doping creates the expected conductive environment where the electric field is reduced to near zero. Of course, in a perfect electrical conductor, the electric field is zero. Here, the doping of the material reduces the amplitude, or strength, of the transmitted electromagnetic energy quickly as it progresses through the substrate. It is expected that the integration of a radiating element onto a semiconductor would be accomplished by using the greatest resistivity of the substrate at the element sight thereby creating the best environment for radiation efficiency. Nearby structures that might experience interactions due to the radiation field should be positioned at a distance from the element so that the wave is attenuated to values below critical limits. The plots above should be useful to semiconductor device designers in finding the minimum separation distance.

Also, it should be noted that an area of impure (doped) substrate could serve to shield other semiconductor devices from electromagnetic energy traveling through the substrate itself by introducing impurities between the antenna element and the devices. Microelectronic devices that might experience interactions from the vicinity of the radiation pattern outside the substrate should be shielded from the electromagnetic energy through the use of current on-wafer packaging techniques.

So, this study shows that the integration of radiating elements onto a semiconductor substrate is a possibility and that electromagnetic interactions are not a hindering barrier.

Areas for continued research in this area include thermal management and packaging techniques. Efforts to minimize packaging to reduce loss in not only single components, but throughout the entire system are and will continue to be of high importance. Our hopes are to enhance performance while creating smaller and lighter systems for use in a military environment, with the ultimate goal being to protect those who serve.

REFERENCES

- [1] Janice C. Rock, "Phased Arrays using Dual-Wafer Fabrication / High-Integration Processes", 2004 IEEE Aerospace Conference Proceedings, March 6-12, 2004.
- [2] Fisher, Dennis and Inder Bahl, *Gallium Arsenide IC Applications Handbook*, pp. 92 – 99, San Diego, CA: Academic Press, 1995.
- [3] Rock, Janice C. and Jim Mullins, "A Mathematical Comparison of Ideal Versus N-Bit Phase Shifters", TR-RD-MG-03-40, September 2003.

- [4] Skolnik, Merrill I., *Introduction to Radar Systems*, pp. 559-560, Boston: McGraw Hill, 2001.
- [5] Fisher, Dennis and Inder Bahl, *Gallium Arsenide IC Applications Handbook*, pp. 92 – 99, San Diego, CA: Academic Press, 1995.
- [6] Downey, A.N., G.E. Ponchak, and R.R. Romanofsky, "Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuits", <http://parts.jpl.nasa.gov/mmhc/3-IX.PDF>.
- [7] S. P. Beeby, A. Blackburn, and N. M. White, "Processing of PZT piezoelectric thick films on silicon for microelectromechanical systems," *J. Micromech. Microeng.* **9** (1999) 218-229.
- [8] E. Zakar, et al., "Process and Fabrication of a PZT thin film pressure sensor," *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A* **19**(1), 1-9 (2001).
- [9] H. G. Yu, et al., "Fabrication and performance of d33-mode lead-zirconate-titanate (PZT) MEMS accelerometers," *MEMS Components and Applications for Industry, Automobiles, Aerospace, and Communication- SPIE Proceedings* **4559** (2001), 130-137.
- [10] Raab, Frederick H et al. "RF and Microwave Power Amplifier and Transmitter Technologies – Part 1", *High Frequency Electronics*, Summit Technical Media (2003): 32-33.
- [11] Pierret, Robert F., *Semiconductor Device Fundamentals*, pp. 86-87, Reading, et al., Addison Wesley Publishing Company, 1996.

BIOGRAPHY

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